

EJP SOIL
ARTEMIS

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

ARTEMIS

Deliverable 5.1

**Framework for on-farm monitoring of the
impact of agroecological systems on soil
quality and soil ecosystem services**

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Executive summary

While LTEs allow for a robust comparison of the impacts of different practices, they often use standardized management that is not necessarily representative and in line with the actual agricultural practices. In contrast, on-farm studies capture a broader range of practices, offering a more representative and diverse view of agroecological implementations. That said, monitoring the impact of these practices on soil health and ecosystem services (ESS) on-farm is more complex.

In this report, we propose a framework for on-farm monitoring of soil health and ecosystem services, with a focus on climate change mitigation and adaptation, sustainable agricultural production, and broader environmental goals. We begin by outlining key definitions and concepts related to agroecology, soil health, and ESS, and review existing frameworks within these contexts.

The proposed framework integrates direct, measurable indicators at the field/farm level, along with indirect indicators derived from management data, tools, models, and remote sensing. We present the theoretical background together with the required data in order to be applied on farm / field level.

Feedback from the ARTEMIS network land users is then presented, followed by a summary of findings. We also draw connections between the proposed indicators, the three pillars of soil health—physical, chemical, and biological—and the selected ecosystem services.

To effectively monitor and assess the long-term impacts of different agroecological practices and to refine models for scaling up, establishing a comprehensive on-farm monitoring system across a network of farms is critical. Such a system would generate valuable insights for policymakers, scientists, and farmers alike, enhancing climate-smart soil management practices and sustainability of agricultural systems. Ultimately, this would contribute to improved soil health and ecosystem services at regional and national levels.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this report

The ARTEMIS project aimed to provide a better understanding of how specific agroecological systems affect soil's ability to mitigate and abate the consequences of climate change. The WP5 – Framework for AE (lighthouse) farm network on soil quality and ecosystem services – aimed to develop and test, on a network of farms, a framework for on-farm monitoring of the impact of diverse AE systems on soil quality and soil related ecosystem services (ESS).

The objective of this report (D5.1) is to provide a monitoring plan with a set of indicators and tools to be used for on-farm monitoring of soil quality and soil-related ESS in diverse AE farms. This protocol and its indicators, parameters, and methods were revised and updated according to the feedback from the land users and results obtained during its use in the field (M5.1).

1.2 Agroecology

Agroecology (AE) can be defined as the application of ecological concepts and principles to design and manage agricultural systems that are productive, environmentally sustainable, and socially just. It is a holistic approach to agriculture and food systems that combines ecological principles with social and economic considerations. It emphasizes the integration of natural processes, biodiversity, and local knowledge to create sustainable and resilient farming systems as well as their social embeddedness into their respective territorial contexts (Hatt* et al., 2016; Wezel et al., 2014). It aims to optimise the interactions between plants, animals, humans, and the environment to avoid the negative environmental and social impacts while maintaining productive agricultural systems (Boeraeve et al., 2020; FAO, 2018; Hatt* et al., 2016; Wezel et al., 2014).

Agroecology embraces a science, a set of practices and a social movement and has evolved over recent decades to expand in scope from a focus on fields and farms to encompass whole agriculture and food systems (Wezel et al., 2020). As a science, it studies ecological processes applied to agricultural systems, while as a movement, it advocates for food sovereignty, social justice, and sustainable land use.

The FAO frames agroecology through 10 Elements (Barrios et al., 2020; FAO, 2018) to guide the transition towards sustainable agriculture and food systems. These elements include diversification of the agricultural and food system, co-creation and sharing of knowledge, building synergies between different elements of the agroecosystem in both time and space, resource-use efficiency, recycling of nutrients, biomass and water within production systems while minimizing external inputs, fostering resilience, emphasis on human and social values, supporting culture and food traditions, providing responsible governance mechanisms and support circular and solidarity economy. Meanwhile, the High-Level Panel of Experts (HLPE) developed 13 consolidated agroecological principles (HLPE, 2019): recycling; input reduction; soil health; animal health; biodiversity; synergy; economic diversification; co-creation of knowledge; social values and diets; fairness; connectivity; land and natural resource governance; participation. These principles are aligned and are complementary to the 10 elements developed by FAO, but they explain the needs for soil and animal health more clear and distinguish between biodiversity and economic diversification (Wezel et al., 2020). Both frameworks highlight agroecology's holistic approach to creating sustainable, equitable food systems that benefit both people and the planet.

Despite the different definitions and concepts, AE places a strong emphasis on the importance of soil quality and recognizes the critical role that soils play in supporting agricultural productivity and ESS. It enhances among others biodiversity and nutrient cycling, while minimizing the use of external inputs and negative environmental impacts. AE promotes a shift from conventional, input-intensive farming practices to more regenerative and resilient approaches that work in harmony with natural processes. By prioritizing ecological sustainability, AE systems contribute to soil conservation, water quality improvement, and climate change mitigation. They also foster biodiversity conservation, enhance food security, and support rural livelihoods.

1.3 Soil quality and soil health

Soil health and quality are two terms that are often used interchangeably like in (Gregorich & Acton, 1995) who provided one of the earliest definitions of both terms: “Soil health, also called soil quality, is defined in agricultural terms as the soil's fitness to support crop growth without becoming degraded or otherwise harming the environment”. The US Department of Agriculture (USDA, 2024) defines these as “the continued capacity of soil to function as a vital living ecosystem that sustains plants, animals, and humans”. Throughout the years several definitions and modifications have appeared for these concepts. Bünemann et al., (2018) concluded that the distinction between these two is a matter of preference and these terms are considered equivalent.

On the other hand, Lehmann et al., (2020) made the claim that soil health is distinct from and broader than soil quality, as soil health extends beyond human health and also includes ESS that refers to a broader planetary health (e.g. biodiversity, carbon sequestration and aesthetics), whereas soil quality focuses on ESS with direct reference to human health (e.g. biomass production and water supply and regulation).

The EJPSoil SIREN project (Faber et al., 2022) made a distinction between soil quality and soil health by associating soil quality with “*the capability of the soil to potentially provide the desired ecosystem services (given soil type, land use and climate) when managed purposefully and sustainably*” and soil health with “*the current capacity of the soil to supply goods and services*” as monitored and measured with dedicated indicators derived from the local soil quality specifications (which are traditionally still called SQIs). The definition of soil health adopted by the EU in the framework of the Soil Monitoring Law (EC, 2023) resonates with such suggestion, considering soil health to “*the physical, chemical and biological condition of the soil determining its capacity to function as a vital living system and to provide ecosystem services*”.

1.4 Soil ecosystem services

1.4.1 Definitions and classifications systems

Throughout human history, our reliance on the natural world for sustenance and well-being has been evident. Ecosystems have consistently provided an array of advantages, including essentials like clean air, water, food, and resources, supporting societies for ages. Yet, it was not until the latter part of the 20th century that these services gained scientific scrutiny and public attention (Westman, 1977). This awareness marked the genesis of the ESS concept, introduced in the early 1980s by (Ehrlich & Ehrlich, 1981) which changed how the understandings of the relationships between nature and human well-being.

Nahlik et al. (2012) summarized several definitions and philosophies that exist in literature regarding the ESS concept. They have shown that primary disagreement among the definitions is whether ESS are directly linked to the benefits provided by ecosystems or if they are associated with the attributes of ecosystems that ultimately lead to these benefits. Nevertheless, one similarity in all these perspectives is that ESS are connected to human benefits (Nahlik et al., 2012).

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003, 2005) defines ESS as "*the benefits that people obtain from ecosystems*". The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity initiative (TEEB, 2008) defines ESS as "*the direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems to human well-being*". SOILS4EU (van der Meulen & Maring, 2018a) extended this definition to "*the goods and services provided by ecosystems that directly and indirectly contribute to human well-being*"; the Soil monitoring law defines ESS as "*the indirect contributions of ecosystems to the economic, social, cultural and other benefits that people derive from those ecosystems*" (EC, 2023). All these sources thus refer to the essential aspect of the ESS concept, that it is an anthropocentric approach.

Various reports and initiatives underscore the intricate nature of ESS. To better understand and manage these services, classification systems have been developed. These systems have the advantage that they offer a common language that enable systematic comprehension, measurement, valuation, mapping, and management of ESS. They enhance communication, awareness, and informed decision-making, aligning with policy and management needs (Breure et al., 2012).

There is no international consensus on what classification system for ESS to use. Numerous classification systems exist, each tailored to a specific research and policy context. For example, Costanza et al., (1997) listed 17 ESS, the IPBES 18 specific categories of nature's contributions to people, while the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment) (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003, 2005) categorized them into provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services. However, MEA's simplicity underserves the cultural dimension. The TEEB classification (TEEB, 2008) focused on economic aspects, adopted MEA categories but excluded "supporting services" and replaced it by "habitat or supporting services." The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018) groups ESS into provisioning, regulation & maintenance, and cultural categories, using a comprehensive hierarchical structure. While more complex, CICES can be used into different scales (local, regional, global) and various ecosystems, from forests to wetlands, making it applicable in diverse contexts, making it useful for specific research, more precise and in-depth analysis.

The choice among classification systems depends on specific research or policy objectives, the level of detail required and the context in which they are applied. The different ESS, as categorized in different classification schemes, are shown in Table 1. Due to the detailed structure and about 90 ecosystem service classes the CICES v5 system (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018) is not presented in the table.

The challenge with different classification systems is that they tackle the categorization issue differently, making comparisons tricky. Despite recent attempts, like including codes from other systems in CICES v5 or using tools like the BBN Ecosystem Service Classification tool (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2016), (<https://openness.hugin.com/example/cices>), achieving agreement on ESS terminology remains a persistent issue (Nahlik et al., 2012; Paul et al., 2021).

Table 1: : The different ecosystem services categories as they appear in different classification systems. The different ESS from each system were connected based on detailed information for each ESS category in the corresponding references, the CICES v5.1 spreadsheet (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018), the BBN ESS classification tool (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2016) and experts' knowledge.

Nature paper (Costanza et al., 1997)	MEA (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003, 2005)	TEEB (de Groot et al., 2010)	IPBES (IPBES, 2019)	
Gas regulation	Air quality regulation	Air quality regulation	3. Regulation of air quality	
Climate regulation	Atmospheric regulation	Climate regulation	4. Regulation of climate	
Disturbance regulation	Natural hazard regulation	Regulation of extreme events	9. Regulation of hazards and extreme events	
Water regulation	Water regulation	Regulation of water flows	6. Regulation of freshwater quantity, location, and timing	
Water supply	Water	Water	7. Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality	
Waste treatment	Water purification and water treatment,	Waste treatment (water purification)		
Erosion control & sediment retention	Erosion regulation	Erosion prevention	8. Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments	
Soil formation	Soil formation	Maintenance of soil fertility (inc. soil formation) and nutrient cycling		
Nutrient cycling				
Pollination	Pollination	Pollination	2. Pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules	
Biological control	Pest regulation	Biological control	10. Regulation of detrimental organisms and biological processes	
	Disease regulation			
Refugia		Maintenance of genetic diversity	1. Habitat creation and maintenance	
		Maintenance of life cycles of migratory species	18. Maintenance of options	
Food production	Food	Food	12. Food and feed	
Raw materials	Fiber, Timber, Ornamental	Raw materials	11. Energy	
		Ornamental resources	13. Materials and assistance	
Genetic resources	Genetic materials	Genetic materials	14. Medicinal, biochemical, and genetic resources	
	Biochemicals, natural medicines, pharmaceuticals	Medicinal resources		
Recreation	Recreation and ecotourism	Recreation and tourism	16. Physical and psychological experiences	
Cultural	Aesthetic values, Knowledge systems and educational values, cultural diversity	Inspiration for culture, art, and design		
		Information and cognitive development		15. Learning and inspiration
		Aesthetic information		17. Supporting identities
	Spiritual and religious values	Spiritual experience		
			5. Regulation of ocean acidification	

1.4.2 Soil and agricultural management related ecosystem services

In the context of soils, the term 'ecosystem service' is often used interchangeably with soil functions or processes, causing confusion and miscommunication. Soil-related ESS specifically rely on the soil's processes and properties. It is crucial to differentiate between soil functions and soil-related ESS. Functions are the ecological processes leading to ESS supply, whereas services are the benefits people directly or indirectly derive from ecosystems (van der Meulen & Maring, 2018a).

Among various ESS classification lists, it is acknowledged that not all services are directly applicable to soils or significantly affected by agricultural practices. To standardize soil-related ESS, (Paul et al., 2021) employed a detailed hierarchical version of CICES v5.1 to create two subsets: one for soil-related ESS and another for ESS linked to agricultural management which are summarized in Table 2. These lists could promote consistent methods for comparable ecosystem service assessments in soil research and potentially serve as assessment guidelines for impact evaluation.

Tables with the detailed description of these ESS together based on CICES version 5.1 classification system (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018) are shown in the Table A1.

Table 2: Shortlist of soil and agricultural management related ESS according to Paul et al., (2021)

CICES code	Biotic provisioning services	CICES code	Biotic cultural services
1.1.1.1	Cultivated terrestrial plants for nutrition	3.1.1.1	Recreation through activities in nature
1.1.1.2	Cultivated terrestrial plants for materials	3.1.1.2	Recreation through observation of nature
1.1.1.3	Cultivated terrestrial plants for energy	3.1.2.3	Culture or heritage from interactions with nature
1.1.5.1	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition	3.1.2.4	Aesthetics from interactions with nature
1.1.5.2	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for materials	3.1.2.1	Scientific interactions with nature
1.1.5.3	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for energy	3.1.2.2	Education and training interactions with nature
1.2.1.1	Genetic material from plants to maintain populations	3.2.1.1	Symbolic meaning of nature
1.2.1.2	Genetic material from plants for breeding	3.2.1.2	Spiritual meaning of nature
CICES code	Biotic regulation & maintenance services	3.2.1.3	Entertainment value of nature
2.1.1.1	Biotic remediation of waste	3.2.2.1	Existence value of nature
2.1.1.2	Biotic filtration, sequestration, and storage of waste	3.2.2.2	Option or bequest value of nature
2.2.1.1	Erosion control	CICES code	Abiotic provisioning services
2.2.1.3	Hydrological cycle and flood control	4.2.1.1	Surface water for drinking
2.2.2.3	Nursery populations and habitats	4.2.1.2	Surface water for non-drinking purposes
2.2.3.1	Pest control (including invasive species)	4.2.2.1	Groundwater for drinking
2.2.3.2	Disease control	4.2.2.2	Groundwater for non-drinking purposes
2.2.4.1	Soil quality by weathering processes	4.3.1.1	Mineral substances for nutrition
2.2.4.2	Soil quality by decomposition and fixing processes	4.3.1.2	Mineral substances for materials

2.2.5.1	Chemical condition of freshwaters	CICES code	Abiotic regulation & maintenance services
2.2.5.2	Chemical condition of salt waters	5.1.1.3	Abiotic filtration, sequestration, and storage of waste
2.2.6.1	Chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans	5.2.1.2	Control of liquid flows
2.2.6.2	Local regulation of air temperature and humidity		
2.2.2.1	Pollination		
2.1.2.3	Visual screening		
2.2.1.2	Mass movement control		
2.2.1.4	Wind protection		
2.2.1.5	Fire protection		
2.2.2.2	Seed dispersal		
2.2.5.2	Chemical condition of salt waters		

1.5 On-farm monitoring frameworks

Several assessment frameworks and tools have been developed and proposed for AE practices performance or to assess where a farm is on the trajectory of transition towards AE. Some of them also consider the link with the different ESS. These frameworks have different spatial scope (from soil to whole-farm or landscape / region level), but also, they consider different dimensions of the AE concept i.e., economic viability, socio-political aspects, environment, and biodiversity, resilience and all the combinations of these dimensions. Moreover, the different frameworks require different data acquisition methods and approaches, such as interviews, questionnaires, qualitative scores, quantitative field measurements, modelling estimates or a combination of these. Table 3 presents a summary of some of the most important assessment tools dedicated to AE.

Apart from the frameworks specifically dedicated to agroecology, there are also several frameworks and assessment tools designed for sustainability, regenerative farming, environmental planning, or ESS assessment, that can be used to evaluate the effects of the different AE practices and/or could inspire the selection of the indicators used in the ARTEMIS framework. Some of these frameworks / tools are presented in Table 4.

Table 3: Assessment tools dedicated to agroecology

Assessment tool	Scope	Indicators	Method data collection	Quantitative or Qualitative?	Activity- or Results-based?	Claimed soil ESS	Scale
TAPE (Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation) [FAO ¹ (FAO, 2019)]	Measure the multi-dimensional performance of agroecological systems across the different dimensions of sustainability	Combination of practices and soil, water, crop & biodiversity parameters	Interview with fixed questionnaire in the characterization framework; Extensive evaluation framework which already includes Visual assessment of soil health, field measurements Agrobiodiversity: calculation tool;	Quantitative and qualitative	Activity & results	Biodiversity Carbon sequestration Climate resilience Erosion control Water (storage & quality)	Farm to landscape
OASIS (Original Agroecology Survey Indicator System) [Agroecology Europe ² (Peeters et al., 2021)]	Analytical framework specifically designed to assess where a farm is on the trajectory of transition towards agroecology.	Level of implementation of various agroecological practices and techniques	Interview & transect walk	Qualitative	Activity	Biodiversity Carbon sequestration Erosion control Flood control Pollination Water (storage & quality)	Farm
GTAE (Handbook for the evaluation of agroecology) ³ [Agence Française de Développement (AFD) (Levard et al., 2019)]	A methodological tool to evaluate the conditions for developing agroecology and the agro-environmental and socio-economic effects of agroecological practices and systems.	Combination of practices and soil, water, crop & biodiversity parameters	Field measurements, soil sampling & lab analysis	Quantitative	Activity & results	Biodiversity Carbon sequestration Erosion control Water (storage & quality)	Farm

¹ <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/tools-tape/en/>

² <https://www.agroecology-europe.org/oasis-brochure/>

³ <https://www.avsf.org/app/uploads/2023/12/memento-gret-uk-web-pages.pdf>

Table 4: Different assessment tools

Assessment tool	Scope	Indicators	Method data collection	Quantitative or Qualitative	Activity- or Results-based	Claimed soil ESS	Scale
SAFA (Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture systems) <i>[FAO (FAO, 2012)]</i>	Sustainability (governance, environment, social and economy (overarching factors).	Environmental integrity indicators (combination of practices and soil, water, crop & biodiversity parameters)	Interview Field measurements, sampling & lab analyses	Qualitative & quantitative	Activity & results	Biodiversity; Carbon sequestration; Flood control; Landslide control; Pollination; Water (storage & quality)	Farm
SAFE (Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment)⁴ <i>[Belgian Federal Science Policy Office (Sauvenier et al., 2005)]</i>	Sustainability (environmental, economic and social pillars)	Sustainability index (combination of practices and soil, water & biodiversity parameters) Ecosystem integrity	No information given	Qualitative	Activity & results	Biodiversity; Carbon sequestration; Climate resilience; Erosion control; Water (storage & quality)	Field to landscape
EFA Calculator (Ecological Focus Areas Calculator)⁵	Assess the potential impact of the ecological focus areas at hand, not the actual impact Semi-natural habitats (or ecological focus	Presence of semi-natural habitats (practices) (Agroforestry, cover, ditches, fallow land, garrigue, hedges or wooden strips, isolated trees, land strips, natural monuments, nitrogen	Area of ecological focus areas entered into software tool (model)	Quantitative	Activity	Carbon sequestration; Erosion control; Flood protection Global climate regulation; Pest control; Water (supply, regulation & quality)	Farm to region

⁴ https://www.belspo.be/belspo/organisation/publ/pub_ostc/CPgen/rappCP28leaflet_en.pdf

⁵ <http://sitem.herts.ac.uk/aeru/efa/>

<p>[European Commission, JRC University of Hertfordshire KU Leuven (Tzilivakis et al., 2015)]</p>	<p>areas) providing ecological services</p>	<p>fixing crops, ponds, short rotation coppice, terrace)</p>					
<p>GAIA biodiversity yardstick⁶</p> <p>[Contract Lifecycle Management (CLM)]</p>	<p>Biodiversity assessment</p>	<p>(Agro)biodiversity on the farm (practices)</p>	<p>Questionnaire (40 questions) entered into GAIA biodiversity yardstick (i.e., online tool) - Gaia2 for livestock or mixed farms, Gaia2arable for large scale arable farms</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Activity</p>	<p>Biodiversity</p>	<p>Farm</p>
<p>Genesis⁷</p> <p>[Genesis]</p>	<p>Sustainability of agricultural supplies, environmental impact & soil health</p>	<p>Combination of practices and soil, water & biodiversity parameters</p>	<p>Sampling and lab analysis</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Activity & results</p>	<p>Biodiversity; Carbon sequestration; Water (quality)</p>	<p>Field to farm</p>
<p>Soil navigator⁸</p> <p>[Wageningen University & Research (WUR)]</p>	<p>Societal functions of agricultural soil</p>	<p>Combination of practices and soil, water & biodiversity parameters</p>	<p>Agroecosystem (country, climatic zone, land use), management (farm management, livestock management, crop management, fertilization, water management, pest management, harvest data), environment (specific climate data, field topography) and soil (soil physical properties, soil chemical properties, soil biology) entered into software tool (model)</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Activity & result</p>	<p>Primary productivity; Water purification and regulation; Biodiversity and habitat provision; Nutrient cycling; Climate regulation</p>	<p>Field to farm</p>

⁶ <https://gaia-biodiversity-yardstick.eu/>

⁷ <https://en.genesis.live/>

⁸ <http://www.soilnavigator.eu/>

2. ARTEMIS framework for on-farm assessment of the impact of AE systems on soil ecosystem services and soil health

2.1 Conceptual framework for monitoring

Within the ARTEMIS WP5 it was aimed to create a framework to monitor on-farm the impact of AE systems on soil related ESS and soil quality.

According to the definitions provided by the EJPSoil Siren project (Faber et al., 2022), dedicated indicators are used to monitoring and measure the current/actual site-specific capacity of the soil to supply goods and services- referred to as soil health, rather than soil quality. Therefore, the scope of this report has been renamed to 'Framework for Monitoring the On-Farm Impact of Agroecological (AE) Systems on Soil-Related Ecosystem Services (ESS) and **Soil Health**.

Also, considering the concept of (Lehmann et al., (2020) in terms that soil health does not solely include human oriented ESS but a wider range of ESS, and the definitions presented in the Soil Monitoring Law (EC, 2023) regarding soil health and regarding sustainable soil management (soil management practices that maintain or enhance the ecosystem services provided by the soil without impairing the functions enabling those services, or being detrimental to other properties of the environment), we focused on creating a framework to assess **soil health** and **soil related ESS** linked to **climate change mitigation** and **adaptation** and also to **sustainable agricultural** production and healthy **environment** more broadly.

Assessing the impact of AE practices on soil health and soil-related ESS requires a comprehensive monitoring framework and system of indicators as well as methods for their calculation and primary data collection. This combines qualitative and quantitative analyses, various data collection methods including farmer surveys, field observations, and participatory soil testing.

The proposed framework is based on three main pillars:

- **Soil Health Assessment:** Focus on determining the physical, chemical, and biological condition of soils under the specific AE practices as required by the Soil Monitoring Law (EC, 2023). Long-term monitoring of these pillars provides insights into the overall health and functionality of the soil ecosystem.
- **Ecosystem Services Assessment:** Assess the ESS provided within the AE systems. Indicators and parameters to evaluate the ESS that are relevant for ARTEMIS, like carbon sequestration, water filtration, storage and supply, and nutrient cycling. By quantifying these services, the framework helps to determine the benefits of the AE practices to humans' well-being and to sustainable soil management.
- **Farmer Participatory Monitoring:** This aspect implies active involvement of farmers in monitoring and evaluating the impacts of AE practices on soil health and ecosystem services. This ensures that local knowledge and farmer experiences are incorporated into the assessment process, fostering co-learning and adaptive management.

2.2 Methodology-Identification of relevant soil health indicators and ESS

Grounded in the theoretical framework's three pillars, we employed surveys in order:

- To shortlist soil and agricultural management related ESS that are relevant in the scope of AE and ARTEMIS.
- To shortlist potential soil and plant indicators to measure the impact of AE practices on soil health by determining the chemical, physical and biological conditions.

The extensive lists of soil health indicators and soil & management related ESS were evaluated and ranked by the WP partners and AE specialists for their relevance and importance to climate change mitigation and adaptation, soil health and environmental sustainability in the different AE systems.

Based on these surveys, we propose a list of direct indicators to be measured on-farm, as well as indirect indicators for a comprehensive assessment of soil health and of the selected ESS.

2.2.1 Selection of ecosystem services

When starting research or analysis on the impact of soil management practices on ESS, it is important to begin with the complete list of soil-related ESS. This ensures that less obvious aspects are not missed. The list then should be narrowed down by considering the specific questions that need to be addressed and the local context, such as the challenges faced by farmers and communities. Additionally, it is crucial to understand the trade-offs between different ESS (Soils4EU, van der Meulen & Maring, 2018b) -- improving one service may reduce the capacity of another. These trade-offs depend on both environmental factors, like climate and soil, and social or political factors in the area.

Thus, in the context of the ARTEMIS project, the comprehensive inventory of ESS associated with soil and agricultural management adopted from Paul et al., (2021) (Table A1) was disseminated among collaborators and scientists having experience with on-farm monitoring of soil health, soil ESS and AE. The extended list of ESS was subjected to evaluation, involving the ranking of services based on their relevance for climate change mitigation and adaptation and significance for the agricultural sustainability of European AE systems. Participants were instructed to prioritize their attention on the specifications of their respective regions and AE farms, while also considering the broader implications for AE systems across Europe. Participants were asked to rank the ESS by assigning scores from 1 to 3, where 1 indicated the highest relevance. An average score was then calculated for each ESS based on the responses (Table A1). To identify the most critical ESS for inclusion in the monitoring framework, the top 25% of the highest-ranking ESS were selected and grouped together based on the CICES V5.1 group name. They are presented in Table 5. For these ESS, relevant for on-farm monitoring soil health indicators and assessment methodologies were attempted to be identified in this monitoring framework.

2.2.2 Selection of soil health indicators

A soil health indicator is a parameter used to quantify and evaluate the impacts of agricultural soil practices on soil health and ESS to draw conclusions for agricultural policy and the effects of the farming practice (modified after Piorr, (2003)).

For the selection of adequate and relevant indicators to evaluate and quantify the effect of the different AE management practices on the ESS and soil health, first the **goals** (e.g. based on ESS

targeted, climate smart AE practices evaluation), the **purpose** (long-term sustainability or short-term effects monitoring) and the **context** (scale of monitoring, what type of cropping systems or farm, soil type, area, etc.) in the different areas should be defined (FAO-ITPS, 2020). This will support the selection of the indicator types, which are suitable for each case and measurement (activity-based or result-based indicators), as well as the assessment approach (modelling, questionnaire and surveys to the farmers, qualitative or quantitative measurements, soil measurements, remote sensing (RS) and earth observation technologies, combination of the previous, etc.).

In the context of the ARTEMIS project, a comprehensive inventory of potential soil and plant indicators to measure the impact of AE practices on soil health and soil related ESS was conducted among the project participants. The partners shared the indicators and methodologies that are used in their context for that purpose. The same partners were also invited to evaluate and rank the list indicators that derived from the inventory that can be used for the on-farm assessment of the impact of agroecological practices on soil health and the provision of ESS. Participants were asked to rank the soil health indicators by assigning scores from 1 to 3, where 1 indicated the highest relevance. Participants were instructed to prioritize their relevance on the parameter's potential for quantifying soil health and the provision of specific ESS, practicability, and cost of the measurement. Also to primarily focus on of their respective regions, while also considering the issues in other regions in Europe. An average score was then calculated for each potential soil health indicator (Table A2) based on the responses. To identify the most critical soil health indicators for inclusion in the monitoring framework, the top 25% highest-ranking were selected and are presented in Table 6.

2.3 Results- Indicators to evaluate impacts of AE on soil health and selected soil ESS

Based on the evaluation and ranking of the different ESS and the potential soil health indicators, a list of ESS and a list with indicators that are needed for measuring the impact of AE practices on soil health (biological, physical, and chemical conditions) and soil related ESS were derived.

For the top 25% highest ranking ESS it was attempted to identify indicators or methods that could be used to evaluate, quantify or/and measure specific aspects/examples of these ESS relevant to the ARTEMIS topic, applicable at farm level (links are shown in Table 9). For this the literature examples of the CICES V5.1 example services and example benefits associated with them, the Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services report of JRC (Maes et al., 2015) as well as indicators from the assessment tools presented in Table 3 and Table 4, and expert knowledge were used.

Considering the needs for the assessment of the different ESS, the evaluation of the soils chemical, physical and biological condition and the aspect that farmers should be included in the monitoring we ended up in a list with indicators that can be directly estimated with soil and farm measurements and indirect indicators that indirectly assess the soil health and ESS through management data, models and tools.

2.3.1 Highest ranking soil and management related ESS and soil health indicators

Within the highest ranked ESS, there are some directly related to climate change mitigation, e.g., 2.2.6.1 Chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans and 2.2.4.2 Soil quality by decomposition and fixing processes, which could correspond to carbon sequestration and processes/practices that promote the improvement of soil quality and the C or/and N fixation in the soil. There are also several ESS which can reduce the effects of a changing climate to agriculture and could be linked to climate

change adaptation, such as the ESS related to extreme events and weather regulation (floods and draughts, high or low for the growing season temperatures, fires etc.), or ESS related to biodiversity maintenance and control (e.g. pest and disease control). Nevertheless, even if from the perspective of climate change adaptation, water storage and water supply are important ESS, they ranked lower by the participants and are not included in the ARTEMIS monitoring framework.

Table 5: The top 25% of the highest-ranking ESS as ranked by the participants surveys, grouped together based on the CICES V5.1 group name.

CICES V5.1 Group	Soil related ecosystems services that considered in the monitoring framework (CICES V5.1 class)
Biomass production	1.1.1.1: Cultivated terrestrial plants grown for nutritional purposes
Greenhouse gas regulation and soil quality	2.2.4.2: Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality; 2.2.6.1: Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere
Erosion and flood control	2.2.1.1: Control of erosion rates; 2.2.1.3: Hydrological cycle & water flow regulation (Including flood control)
Water quality	2.1.1.1, 2.1.1.2: Bioremediation / Filtration / sequestration / storage / accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals; 2.2.5.1: Chemical quality regulation of freshwaters
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	2.2.3.1, 2.2.3.2: Disease and pest control; 2.2.2.1, 2.2.2.3: Pollination, Maintaining nursery populations and habitats

The soil health indicators were categorized to chemical, physical and biological, and also indicators related to the inherent properties of soil and the environments were also included. Among the highest-ranking soil health indicators, many relate to the different components of soil organic matter and nitrogen, highlighting their importance for soil health and ESS related to climate change mitigation.

Table 6: The top 25% of the highest-ranking soil health indicators as ranked by the participants surveys.

Type	Indicator	Rank
Chemical	Total and potential mineralizable N	1.08
Chemical	Total soil organic carbon (SOC) content	1.15
Chemical	pH	1.15
Biological	Crop yield	1.15
Physical	Dry bulk density (ρ_b)	1.23
Biological	Soil cover	1.23
"Inherent"	Texture	1.23
"Inherent"	Precipitation	1.23
Chemical	SOC stock	1.25
Biological	Biomass production	1.25
"Inherent"	Climate	1.25
Chemical	Exchangeable K, Ca, Na, Mg	1.31
Chemical	Total soil organic matter (SOM)	1.33
Chemical	C/N ratio	1.38
"Inherent"	Soil type	1.38
Physical	Plant-available water	1.42
Chemical	Easily degradable organic matter (Hot water extractable C - HWC)	1.42
Biological	Earthworms	1.42

It was also observed that biological indicators, particularly those directly related to soil fauna, are not ranked within the top 25% despite their recognized importance for soil health. This may be due to the lack of consensus within the scientific community on universally accepted representative indicators,

the complexity and variability of measuring soil organisms, high costs, and challenges in linking these indicators to specific ecosystem functions.

2.3.2 Indicators for direct assessment of soil health and ESS (Field and lab measurements)

Based on the inventory ranking but also on the discussions with farmers and experts on agroecology and field monitoring the following soil health indicators (Table 7) were selected to be used in ARTEMIS with the scope to facilitate a basis for longer term monitoring in the selected farms.

Table 7: Direct indicators to be measured/evaluated on field

Indicator	Comments/Rational
Soil texture (Soil type)	Needs to be defined once. Important to interpret results for several other parameters.
Bulk density	Highly important for C stock estimations
Penetration resistance & moisture content	Can relate to soil compaction and water dynamics. Since soil penetration resistance is inversely related to soil water content, normalization of soil water content is necessary for effective comparison of SPR data. Thus, soil moisture content should be measured at the same time as penetration resistance.
Visual soil assessment for soil structure (VESS)	https://soils.vidacycle.com/soil-tests/vess-visual-evaluation-of-soil-structure/ A straightforward and practical method for characterising and scoring soil structural and physical quality. Direct way to raise awareness and the farmers to have an idea of their soil health
Total soil organic carbon content	Highly important parameter for soil health and climate regulation. Interesting to measure at 0-10 cm, 10-30 cm and if possible deeper
Total N	Highly important parameter for soil health, climate regulation and environmental pollution. Interesting also for the farmers in terms of fertilization requirements.
Plant-available P	Important parameter for soil health and environmental pollution. Interesting also for the farmers in terms of fertilization requirements.
exchangeable K	Important parameter for soil health. Interesting also for the farmers in terms of fertilization requirements.
pH	Important to interpret results for several other parameters, like the availability of plant nutrients.
Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	Highly important parameter for soil health and nutrient availability. Can relate to several ESS related to water quality and water pollution
Earthworms	Easily applicable and can be used for demonstration and awareness raising which is important in the general context of agroecology
Microbial activity	Among the biological related indicators, these parameters received high scores. It is acknowledged that among the scientific community there is no consensus on the best biological indicators for each case.
Microbial biomass	There are several ongoing projects on this purpose and their conclusions are foreseen to support the future refinement of this part
Total aboveground biomass	It is an important parameter to be used in N balance modelling investigations, to estimate C input returns to soil as well as to support the calibration and validation of satellite imageries. The estimation of biomass production is crop dependant. It is advisable to follow the same protocols per crop in order to have comparable results across time and space.

2.3.2. Indicators for indirect assessment of soil health and ESS (Management indicators- proxies – models- tools)

The methods for indirect estimation of soil health play a significant role nowadays due to their ability to offer an understanding of soil health without the resource-intensive requirements of direct measurements. Direct measurements typically involve laborious and time-consuming analyses of various physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil, often necessitating extensive fieldwork and laboratory procedures. In contrast, indirect methods offer a more pragmatic and resource-efficient approach by assessing the soil through combining (management) data, remote sensing (RS), models and tools. This resource efficiency is crucial for conducting large-scale and continuous assessments, allowing for more frequent monitoring of soil conditions. Management data can relate to RS information and serve as input for predictive models. This integration enables a real-time evaluation of the impact of various management strategies on soil health, contributing to more informed decision-making in agriculture and land management.

However, it is essential to acknowledge the challenges and limitations that accompany these methods, particularly in terms of reliability, robustness, and accuracy. The reliance on proxies and models introduces uncertainties, as these indicators may not perfectly mirror the complex and site-specific nature of soil properties. Additionally, the success of indirect estimation depends on the availability, reliability, and accuracy of input data at the spatial and temporal resolution required for the different soil health and ESS assessments. Incomplete or inaccurate information may compromise the reliability of assessments, highlighting the need for robust data collection and validation protocols. Researchers and practitioners are actively working towards enhancing the robustness of these methods through improved data collection, validation protocols, and the incorporation of advanced technologies.

The positive attributes associated with indirect estimation methods together with the need for upscaling have brought considerable interest within the scientific community to address the limitations and to ensure that indirect estimation methods can stand alone as reliable tools for comprehensive soil health assessments. Nevertheless, a more pragmatic and effective strategy for soil health and ESS monitoring and assessment lays on a balanced approach, combining the strengths of both classical and indirect methods, i.e., integrate these approaches into soil health assessments together with classical soil surveys at farm/field level.

Considering the list of soil health indicators and the possible ways for monitoring and evaluating the prioritized ESS as derived from the two ARTEMIS inventories, here we propose some indirect methods and assessment tools that could replace some direct on-field or laboratory measurements or that could work complementary. Always in a monitoring framework it is advisable to evaluate the ESS that are prioritized, the available sources, the level of detail and accuracy required for the specific purpose and select indicators accordingly.

Plant available water

The plant available water which was ranked within the 25% most relevant soil health indicators, refers to the portion of soil water that plants can absorb and use for growth. It is crucial indicator for agriculture because it directly affects crop health, yield, and resilience to drought, and influences the availability of moisture for soils' biota, which contribute to land productivity and biological soil health. It is determined by the difference between field capacity which is the water retained in the soil after excess drainage and wilting point where the plant can no longer extract water from the soil.

How much water a particular type of soil can retain under different pressure heads (pressure needed to extract that water) is described by the soil water retention curve (WRC), also known as the soil moisture characteristic curve or pF curve. This curve is characteristic for each different soil.

Various methods, both in the field and laboratory, can be employed to determine the WRC. However, due to their time-consuming nature and the extensive effort involved, often the use of analytical models or regression equations is preferred. These empirical formulas, known as pedotransfer functions (PTF), enable the prediction of WRC values which serve for the determination of various indicators (i.e. field capacity, wilting point and thus plant-available water) based on readily measurable or pre-defined soil properties (Román Dobarco et al., 2019; Tóth et al., 2015). Here we propose the PTFs from Toth et al, 2015 for estimating the soil water content at field capacity and at wilting point, which have been calibrated with soil data from all over Europe. However, it is advisable, if available, in each region to use PTFs that have been developed and calibrated with datasets from the same geographical origin and similar pedological domains (Román Dobarco et al., 2019).

(Tóth et al., 2015) proposed several different PTFs for prediction of the water content at FC and WP using linear regression models, depending on the data availability.

The PTFs in form of a linear regression model, that are listed below, are more suitable for comparing farm practices than those that only consider textural characteristics. This is because farm practices influence soil organic carbon levels, which in turn affect the bulk density and of pore space. The proposed PTFs use the soil organic carbon content (OC; %), clay (0-2 μm) and silt (2-50 μm) content percentages.

$$\theta_{FC(-330\text{ cm})} = 0.2449 - 0.1887 * (1/(OC+1)) + 0.004527 * CI + 0.001535 * Si + 0.001442 * Si * (1/(OC+1)) - 0.00005110 * Si * CI + 0.0008676 * CI * (1/(OC+1))$$

$$\theta_{WP(-15000\text{ cm})} = 0.09878 + 0.002127 * CI - 0.0008366 * Si - 0.07670 * (1/(OC+1)) + 0.00003853 * Si * CI + 0.002330 * CI * (1/(OC+1)) + 0.0009498 * Si * (1/(OC+1))$$

An open-source available R package ([eupftf](#) package) is available to support the selection and estimation of the PTF based on the available input data and desired output or for different pressure heads.

Data that are required
Textural characteristics e.g. silt content and clay content
Soil organic carbon content

Soil cover

Soil cover, that was also ranked within the 25% most relevant indicators for soil health, refers to standing living plant vegetation. Maintaining the cover of the soil throughout the year can reduce soil erosion, water runoff and nutrient leaching (only by standing vegetation) and can contribute to maintaining or increasing soil organic matter.

To monitor the soil coverage throughout the year several approaches can be used. Apart from on field measurements such as the estimation of plant cover in quadrats which is time consuming, estimations can be done by either knowing the crop presence, sowing and harvesting dates from the management logs of each farm, the different Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS) often provided by private companies, the Area Monitoring System (AMS) or the Land parcel information system (LPIS) or by using different vegetation indices combined with RS data.

For example, the Fraction of Vegetation Cover (FCover) index corresponds to the fraction of ground covered by green vegetation. It can easily be monitored throughout the year at the field or farm level as it can be derived from the freely available Sentinel-2 satellite images ([FCOVER \(Fraction of green Vegetation Cover\) | Sentinel Hub custom scripts \(sentinel-hub.com\)](#)). These imageries can be calibrated for the local context for more precise results as in Terrascope (<https://terrascope.be/en/sectors/agriculture>), that provides the FCover index calibrated for Belgium and the Netherlands.

Soil water erosion and water regulation

Two ESS classes that ranked as relevant for the context of ARTEMIS was the control of erosion rates and the regulation of the water cycle and water flow. Water regulation includes several ESS, such as water retention and storm and high-water protection (including flood control). These water regulation services are closely related to other regulating ESS, such as erosion and sedimentation control and water purification.

To evaluate the effect of the different AE practice on the erosion rates different visual observations can be used, even from farmers, to assess the presence or extent of current soil erosion on their farms. Some common observations of soil erosion are soil textural changes, as finer particles are more transported by erosion processes than coarser ones, leading to a coarser soil texture and as deeper soil layers becoming visible at the top layers when they are eroded. The outcrop of deeper layers might also change soil colour, as topsoil often contains more soil organic matter and is darker. Also changes in the surface roughness can provide indirect evidence of erosion and sedimentation. Smooth surfaces may indicate higher erosion rates compared to rougher surfaces. Down-slope sediment can be visible, (partially) covering plant (seedlings). The formation of gullies or rills in the landscape is also a visible sign of significant erosion. Monitoring the presence and extent of gullies or rills can indicate severe erosion in specific areas of the farm.

Indirect indicators related to the field management can provide valuable insights about the current erosion risk and water regulation which have an impact on soil health. For example, the coverage or not of the soil through the year and the applied tillage practices can have direct impacts on the soil water infiltration, soil structure and soil compaction which directly influence the soil water erosion rates, and the water flow cycle.

Soil water erosion rates

Soil Tillage Intensity Rating (STIR)

Tillage method and intensity have been proven to affect the erosion rates and soil loss (Mhazo et al., 2016). An indirect index for soil erosion likelihood could be the RUSLE2-based Soil Tillage Intensity Rating (STIR) proposed by the USDA (<https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-11/CEAP-Croplands-2008-Methodology-SoilTillageIntensityRating.pdf>). It is determined by management practices for a specific field for the entire rotation or single crops. The STIR value reflects the type and severity of soil disturbance caused by tillage operations. Key components considered in the calculation of STIR include the tillage type and depth, the operational speed, and the percentage of the soil surface disturbed. Apart from these, all the operations involved in fertilizing, planting, controlling weeds, harvesting the crop, and managing residues are evaluated in the STIR rating. Lower values of STIR reduce the likelihood of sheet, rill, and wind erosion. STIR ratings for example are improving with lower

intensity of tillage but also using soil conservation crops like alfalfa or grass or cover crops in the rotation.

Data that are required

Tillage type and date, operational speed of tillage equipment, tillage depth, percent of soil surface area disturbed

Modelling and remote sensing techniques

On areas with high-risk potential monitoring of soil erosion at the farm/field level can be enhanced and complemented by modelling approaches and RS techniques, resulting in a more pragmatic assessment. Empirical models like the USLE/RUSLE (Universal Soil Loss Equation/Renewed Universal Soil Loss Equation) rely on factors such as rainfall, soil erodibility, slope length, land cover, and conservation practices to estimate soil erosion rates over time and identify erosion-prone areas.

Nowadays, advancements allow for the improvement of these factors and their realistic representation through coupling with various RS products and information, such as detailed digital elevation models, soil properties maps, and higher-resolution land cover maps (Almagro et al., 2019; Kazamias & Sapountzis, 2018; Panagos et al., 2015; Quemada & Daughtry, 2016). Moreover, spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), the Normalized Difference Tillage Index (NDTI), the Shortwave Infrared Normalized Difference Residue Index (SINDRI) or the Cellulose Absorption Index (CAI) (Almagro et al., 2019; Quemada & Daughtry, 2016) offer valuable insights into vegetation health, soil cover, and crop residues, critical elements influencing soil erosion dynamics, and especially the vegetation cover factor (C-factor).

The C-factor's value mainly depends on the vegetation's cover percentage and growth stage and is the most crucial factor that quantifies the human impact on soil erosion. Depending on the required level of analysis and available sources, different approaches can be followed. In many cases and regions average values of C-factor per crop type and soil management exist, derived from literature, or assessed through expert knowledge. Nevertheless, in croplands the soil and crop parameters change between and within the years. This demands the estimations of the C-factor and erosion to be calculated frequently enough over the course of a year or a crop rotation to provide an adequate measure of how they change.

Remote sensing, particularly from optical sensors like Sentinel-2, offers potential for tracking vegetation phenology to inform the C-factor (Matthews et al., 2023), especially when combined with SAR data (e.g., Sentinel-1) or other multispectral sensors (e.g., Landsat) to overcome cloud cover. The analyses of the spectral indices can provide detailed information regarding crop annual changes (sowing and harvesting dates, growth stage, residue amount etc) and contribute to refining the C factor and the erosion risk (Almagro et al., 2019; Panagos et al., 2015). However, challenges remain, such as underestimating canopy cover and overestimating soil loss ration during periods of vegetation senescence. Tillage practices and residue cover, critical during and after harvest periods, are difficult to predict at large scales due to uncertainties caused by factors like soil moisture and surface roughness. This underscores the importance of regional knowledge to reduce uncertainty in C-factor estimates as the lack of field data provide some limitations to the application of remote sensing data and related methods (Zhang et al., 2011).

Data that are good to have for validation and model improvement
Sowing and harvesting dates of crops and cover crops
Tillage method and intensity
Residue amount left on field, amount that incorporated, amount that just left on top

Water cycle and water flow regulation

Monitoring the effectiveness of agricultural management practices on the regulation of water flows and the water cycle on a farm level can be conducted both with direct and indirect approaches. Soil infiltration rates serve as a fundamental indicator, reflecting how well the soil absorbs water and reduces surface runoff, thereby mitigating flood potential. Monitoring changes in **soil structure and compaction** can also provide insights into improvements in infiltration capacity over time. Nevertheless, also **management information** about the applied practices can be used as indicators for flood regulation. The **presence and health of vegetative / grass buffer zones**, such as riparian strips or cover crops, or the planting of hedgerows, practices that are commonly used in AE, are indirect indicators that the agricultural systems help restrict the flow of storm water, carrying sediment and nutrients, and prevents them from being washed from the field into the watercourse, roads and neighbouring properties. These buffers help to stabilize soil, reduce erosion, and absorb excess water during heavy rainfall events and lowering flood risk.

Models and RS

Additionally, models to simulate runoff and flood dynamics based on farm-level data, can provide quantitative assessments of flood risk, and water cycle dynamics. The approaches vary from traditional hydrological models through specific tools incorporated into integrated modelling frameworks to conceptual approaches with non-water models used in combination with water-based models (Nedkov et al., 2022). The hydrological model SWAT is the most popular modelling tool in the assessment of water-related ES due to its long history of development and popularity among hydrologists.

As with erosion, RS data can provide valuable information for monitoring flood risk and water dynamics on a farm level. High-resolution satellite imagery can be used to monitor land cover changes, vegetation health, and surface water dynamics, which are important indicators of water flow and flood risk as well as information on soil moisture content and flood extent, which are useful for flood risk assessment. LiDAR data can provide detailed information about terrain elevation, slope, and surface roughness, which are critical inputs for hydrological models used to simulate flood dynamics. By integrating farm-scale hydrological models with RS data, farmers and stakeholders can gain a better understanding of flood risk dynamics and assess the effectiveness of flood mitigation measures implemented at the farm level.

Data that are required
Cover crop presence, presence of buffer strips, hedgerows or other landscape features
Climate data

Soil compaction

Another risk caused by the machinery used in a field is soil compaction. Soil compaction reduces soil life, permeability to water and air, and the possibilities for plant growth. Apart from the direct measurements of penetration resistance, the model Terranimo® (<https://www.terranimodk/>) (Schjøning & Lamandé, 2020) can also be used to predict the risk of soil compaction by farm machinery. It compares vertical stresses from wheels with soil strength. It is based on realistic operating conditions and management data. These data include the type of the machinery, loading weight, tyre type and pressure, to estimate the stresses exerted by wheels from machinery driving on the soil. The site description to estimate soil strength includes the soil textural characteristics, soil organic matter, bulk density, and matric potential or soil water content in the different depths of the soil profile. Predefined databases per country, make it easier for the user as it estimates the required soil information based on the soil type, and the required soil water information based on the wetness of the soil (dry, moist, or wet). The results gained may help identify the most beneficial traffic systems (wheel configurations, tyre types, traffic conditions) for sustainable farming that minimizes compaction risk.

Data that are required for application of the model

Tractor or machinery type, tyre type, tyre pressure and load

Soil type or textural characteristics, organic matter content & bulk density per soil layer

Soil wetness (dry, moist, wet) or water content / matric potential per soil layer

Figure 1: Interface of the Terranimo® model

Water quality

In addition to ecosystem services (ESS) related to water cycle regulation, those linked to water quality ranked as also relevant in the context of agriculture and AE. Water quality can be compromised by various management practices that contribute to soil pollution, leading to the degradation of soil water, water bodies, and aquifers. Examples of these harmful practices include excessive or poorly managed fertilization, the overuse of phytosanitary products, and irrigation with low-quality water, such as brackish water. These actions can severely impact water quality.

In the ARTEMIS framework, direct indicators such as Total Nitrogen (N), exchangeable Phosphorus (P), and exchangeable Potassium (K), and Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) are included as key parameters for assessing soil health, as they are linked to both soil and water pollution. These indicators help to evaluate the nutrient balance and potential contamination risks. Additionally, an indirect indicator of soil pollution risk is included in the ARTEMIS framework—based on the amount of phytosanitary products applied by farmers on their fields, which is derived from management data.

Pollution risk, pest, and disease management

The indicator of Frequency of Treatment (IFT) emerges as a key metric for soil pollution risk. It was developed by the French Ministry of Agriculture and the French National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA) in 2006 (<https://agriculture.gouv.fr/indicateur-de-frequence-de-traitements-phytosanitaires-ift#section-2>). Encompassing herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides, IFT serves as a comprehensive gauge of pesticide application and their evolution over time. Its primary objective lies in the comparison between the actual dose administered and the recommended dose for the different crops, thereby furnishing an average index reflective of phytosanitary products utilization across agricultural landscapes. It can be used as an agricultural development tool allowing farmers to carry out an AE diagnosis, to question their system.

At the farm scale, for each product applied to an agricultural plot, the IFT is calculated based on the ratio of the dose used by the farmer to the standard dose (when the applied dose is equal to the standard dose IFT=1). By summarizing the IFT of all products applied to each agricultural field each year the average IFT of the farm can be estimated. The online tool to calculate the IFT and to find also reference doses that correspond to each crop and product (in French) can be found here <https://alim.agriculture.gouv.fr/ift/>

Data that are required
Product type and dose used
Date of application
Recommended dose of product (optional as there is a database)
Crop type

Carbon sequestration

Soil health indicators related to soil organic carbon (SOC content, SOC stocks, HWC, C:N ratios), as well as ESS related to the decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality and to climate regulation, were ranked by the partners among the 25 % most important soil health indicators and ESS

(See Appendix). This is no surprise as soil organic carbon is key for many soil functions and important for climate change mitigation.

Quantifying the impact of AE practices on the mass of organic carbon stored in the soil is not easy as carbon sequestration is a gradual process that may take years or decades to observe significant changes. Therefore, it is important to implement monitoring programs over a long time period.

Apart from the need to monitor over long time periods, we need to understand that SOC contents and stocks are the result of carbon inputs by both crop residues, and organic fertilisation, that are partly humified and incorporated in SOC, and mineralisation processes and root exudates feeding the rhizosphere microorganisms. Each year, part of the SOC is mineralised again and converted back to CO₂. Whether SOC will increase, or decrease will thus depend both on yearly inputs and turnover. When changing management practices SOC will increase or decrease until, often after decades, a steady state is reached. However, soils in an agricultural context are seldom in steady state. Therefore, the impact of AE practices on SOC changes (tonC/ha.year) should be compared with SOC changes under business-as-usual practices (when conventional practices are maintained, also called 'baseline'). Don et al., (2024) have pointed out that SOC enhancing practices might not always lead to carbon sequestration, which is a transfer of carbon from the atmosphere to the soil). Instead, these practices could also lead to SOC loss mitigation when SOC is decreasing under BAU practices. Therefore, Don et al. (2023) have introduced the term 'SOC accrual' which is the increase in SOC at a given unit of land compared to a BAU value. SOC accrual could result in carbon sequestration as well as in SOC loss mitigation or both.

SOC changes could be determined directly with measure-remeasure approaches or indirectly estimated with models, that could be combined with measurements for the initial soil conditions and/or remote sensing for providing the necessary inputs to the model.

Usually, SOC and SOC changes can be measured directly (Bispo et al., 2021) by soil samples and laboratory analyses or proximal sensing or by measuring carbon fluxes with eddy covariance systems or chambers connected to gas analysers, combined with detailed measurements of carbon inputs by organic fertiliser and outputs (harvest). In fact, most of these direct methods provide accurate data but are time-consuming, costly, and challenging to apply on a large scale. Moreover, when using measure-remeasure approaches we assume the baseline is in steady state (SOC change under BAU is 0 tonC / ha.year), which is usually not the case. The SOC change detected by measure-remeasure approaches might thus not completely reflect the impact of the AE practice change. This could be overcome by installing control plots where BAU is maintained and that have comparable management history and soil conditions. But also control plots add to additional costs and two fields are never completely comparable.

Therefore, indirect estimations are often attempted, especially in large-scale monitoring, such as for Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) for carbon farming. Smith et al., (2020) and Batjes et al., (2024) propose an approach in which models are informed as much as possible with existing data layers and remote sensing and that are calibrated against a network of long-term field experiments and monitoring sites. Apart from the possibility for upscaling, SOC models have the advantage that they also can be used to predict the impact of multiple management scenarios, which can help stakeholders to identify optimal strategies for enhancing carbon storage.

Regarding modelling, soil process-based models such as the Roth-C or AMG are used to simulate carbon dynamics in agricultural soils. These models integrate data on climate, soil properties, crop management practices, and land use history to estimate changes of carbon storage over time. Other,

simpler, tools also exist, such as the humus balance tools, (e.g., humusbilanz.ch) which makes a yearly balance between how much carbon is humified and how much carbon is mineralised. These kinds of tools are often used as decision support tool for farmers. Soil models could be coupled to crop growth models, such as the AquaCrop, or the CropSyst models, to simulate crop productivity and carbon inputs to soils, or alternatively ecosystem models, such as STICS, DNDC could be used to simulate both the plant and soil compartment.

The drawback of models is that it requires many input parameters, such as input data on initial soil conditions, weather, management, and crop growth. RS has the potential to deliver some of these input parameters, which makes it easier for upscaling. An example is the use of RS for estimating aboveground biomass and resulting carbon inputs to soils (e.g. Wijmer et al., (2024)).

Modelling can support and complement long-term and large-scale monitoring, but we have to keep in mind that there are also uncertainties associated with parameterization and simplification of complex processes and their accuracy depends on the availability and quality of input data. RS allows for consistent and standardized methodologies for continuous monitoring of large areas. Nevertheless, there also some drawbacks such as the fact that the interpretation of RS data requires specialized skills and expertise both in geospatial analysis and RS technologies, the data processing and analysis can be computationally intensive, and that the data quality and availability are still an important research topic (effects of cloud cover and data gaps). Also, most of the RS techniques require validation with ground-based measurements to ensure accuracy, which can be resource-intensive as well as requiring consistent calibration of the sensors.

Data that can support modelling
Organic fertilization: date, frequency, amount and type, quality
Mineral fertilization: date, dose, type
Crop rotation, catch crop / intermediate crop types, harvesting and showing dates
Residue management (buried, exported, etc.)
Tillage type, (at least: ploughing vs no tillage), depth
Crop yield, biomass
Irrigation date and amount

Crop diversity

Although not amongst the 25% highest ranked soil health indicators by the WP partners (but in the 25-50%), crop and plant diversity is retained in the ARTEMIS monitoring framework as it is part of the 10 elements of Agroecology of the FAO (FAO, 2018). Intensification and specialization are often leading to standardized landscapes and agricultural practices, with subsequent losses in terms of biodiversity (Tiemann et al., 2015). Crop diversity is increasingly considered as a component of the sustainability of agroecosystems. Crop diversification and crop rotational diversity at farm and field scales can be estimated using farm records of the rotation and spatial crop selection practices but also several indices and metrics have been used for the quantification of the abundance and evenness (how similar

the abundances of different species are in the community) of the different crops, as well as the intensity of the rotations. Examples are the crop diversification indices Shannon diversity, Herfindhal and the Ogive index or the crop diversification indexes for richness and evenness, and the crop rotation complexity indices (Basavaraj et al., 2016; Mzyece et al., 2023; Simson, 1949).

Here the Shannon diversity index is proposed because it incorporates the number of different crop species (richness) and the relative abundance or proportion of each species (evenness) and is sensitive to the presence of both common and rare species (abundance) which is important in agroecological systems aiming for balanced and sustainable crop distribution (Nilsson et al., 2022; Schaak et al., 2023; Spellerberg & Fedor, 2003). The proportion of species i relative to the total number of species (p_i) is calculated, and then multiplied by the natural logarithm of this proportion ($\ln(p_i)$). The resulting product is summed across species, and multiplied by -1:

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^S [p_i \cdot \ln(p_i)]$$

where,

H: Shannon diversity index

p_i : proportion of individuals of i -th species in a whole community ($p_i = n/N$, where n : individuals of a given type/species; and N : total number of individuals in a community)

The higher the value of H , the higher the diversity of species in a particular community. The lower the value of H , the lower the diversity. A value of $H = 0$ indicates a community that only has one species.

For examples and tool to estimated it see Bobbit, (2021) and Rain, (2024).

Data that are required

Crop species, cover crop species, landscape features

Climate and weather

Climate is also included in the 25% most relevant indicators for soil health monitoring as inherent property of the system. Climate data analysis provide crucial information about the environmental conditions that directly impact soil health and fertility. By integrating climatic and weather data into soil health monitoring programs, researchers, farmers, and land managers can better understand and interpret how environmental conditions influence soil processes and make informed decisions to sustainably manage and improve soil health. The climate conditions are also often used in crop, soil, and ecosystem models.

Climatic and weather data in different special and temporal scales can be obtained in high quality from several open-source datasets like:

- The daily gridded observational dataset for precipitation, temperature, sea level pressure, global radiation, and wind speed in Europe E-OBS which currently it is maintained and elaborated as part of the [Copernicus Climate Change Services](#)

- The CHELSA (Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface areas) high resolution (30 arc sec, ~1km) global downscaled climate data set currently hosted by the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL. It provides free access to high resolution climate data for research and application and is constantly updated and refined. (<https://chelsa-climate.org/>)
- The Copernicus European Regional ReAnalysis (CERRA) sub-daily regional reanalysis data for Europe on single levels from 1984 to present (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-cerra-single-levels?tab=overview>,)
- ERA5-Land hourly data from 1950 to present (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-land?tab=overview>.)

3 Appling the framework on farm

In this chapter, we present how the proposed framework can be applied on-farm to assess the effects of agroecological (AE) practices on soil health and soil related ESS. It provides a foundation for consistent and reliable monitoring that supports the long-term evaluation of the cropping systems.

3.1 Comparison to an adjacent control

Given the great variability of the soil properties and of the AE cropping systems, even within the same area, it is recommended to establish a **control** plot, to evaluate practice effects. Just measuring initial conditions prior to practice change will not be sufficient, since also under the business-as-usual practices (BAU) (soil) parameters might be changing as soils are often not in steady state and it does not account for the effects of climate change that would also occur under BAU. This means that, preferably, the obtained value(s) must be compared with value(s) measured in an adjacent area, where AE measures have not been applied (control) but with comparable history and soil conditions.

3.2 Analysis protocols

The samples taken in control and AE monitoring plots must be taken with the same sampling protocols and under the same conditions (same weather conditions, same stage of crop cycle). The soil samples must also be analysed using the same laboratory methods. As identified by the EJP SOIL D6.3 (Bispo et al., 2021) it is preferable that the analysis and sampling protocols are not standardized between the countries, but better harmonized, in order not to break the connection with past measurements, impair the use of existing data, but also because the infrastructure and knowledge already present.

Here, only indicators were proposed, and each partner was responsible and able to select and proceed with the protocols already used or preferred.

3.3 Area of sampling

The selected sampling areas must be representative for the field or farm to be assessed. Odd spots or extraordinary conditions of the field (e.g., tractors routes, headlands, manure storage sites) should be avoided.

To be able to compare and harmonize the direct measured soil data with proximal and remote sensing data it is proposed that the sampling area within each field will be in line with the SENTINEL-2 satellites smallest spatial resolution of 10m*10m (i.e. pixel). Soil and crop data and field observations need to be geo-referenced in order to make them comparable to RS imagery. To ensure that the ground truth

data collection aligns with the spatial scale of the Sentinel-2 imagery, taking into account the pixel size and resolution, first we have to obtain the Sentinel-2 satellite imagery covering the farm area of interest and to determine the spatial resolution of the Sentinel imagery. Sentinel-2 typically senses multiple spectral bands with varying spatial resolutions (e.g., 10m, 20m, and 60m). Then we have to create a grid overlay on the Sentinel-2 image using Geographic Information System (GIS) software or similar tools. Within each grid cell, sampling points should be selected randomly to try to cover the pixel-scale variability in the (soil) parameters of interest.

Figure 2: Proposed sampling plots within each field of each farm

3.4 Frequency and timing of sampling

The frequency of the measurements depends on the nature of the practice to be assessed and the indicators. For most AE practices, where the objective is to obtain long-term results, the positive impacts may be observed within a time frame of 4 - 5 years or more after implementation.

3.5 Documentation, storage and analysis of the monitoring and farm management data

Within ARTEMIS a template was created for both the collection and storage of the monitoring (meta)data coming from the proposed monitoring framework as well as for storing farm management data that are required for estimation of the indirect indicators, the interpretation of the monitoring results and analysis. The template (Panagea & Vanderhasselt, 2024) is available in the ARTEMIS zenodo community. For the template, we have started from the format and coding of the EJPSOIL SoilX management data template (Heller, Wittwer, et al., 2024), the EJPSOIL LTE meta data template (Blanchy et al., 2023) and the SoilCare database template (Panagea et al., 2021) but made some modification to cover the needs and requirements of the ARTEMIS on-farm monitoring framework. It is vital for each sampling plot within each field to specify the coordinates to be able to connect the management information and measurements with tools and proxies coming from satellites, drones etc.

When farmers make use of it, management information could be extracted from Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS), that exist for both commercial and scientific reasons. In the future, the Artemis template could be connected to FMIS (both for extracting management as for providing

monitoring info to the FMIS), as each entry is recorded with unique IDs and combinations of ID as in relational databases.

Some of the indirect indicators proposed in the monitoring framework, considering that all the management data for their calculation are available, can be estimated and calculated by the new R-package SoilManageR (Heller, Chervet, et al., 2024). The SoilManageR is a compilation of functions to calculate numerical agricultural soil management indicators derived from a management timeline of an arable field. Currently, indicators for carbon (C) input into the soil system based on allometric equations, soil tillage intensity rating (STIR), number of soil cover and living plant cover days, N fertilization and livestock intensity, and plant diversity (Shannon index) are implemented. The functions can also be used independently of the management timeline to calculate some indicators. R packages are open source and can be improved by the science community. It is thus feasible to include additional indicators like the Indicator of Frequency of Treatment for plant (IFT). The inputs of this package follow the format of the EJPSOIL SoilX management data template and subsequently the ARTEMIS DB template.

Feedback from land users on the monitoring framework

A survey was conducted among farmers participating in the ARTEMIS WP5 project to gather feedback on the proposed monitoring framework. These farmers have been applying AE practices for more than five years, and in many cases, for over ten years. In several instances, improvements in soil health are already noticeable.

Regarding the main changes observed following the implementation of AE practices, farmers reported yields comparable to those under traditional conventional management, but with greater stability over time. Significant improvements in soil conditions were also noted, including better aggregation, increased organic matter content, enhanced aggregate stability, improved workability, faster water infiltration, and better moisture retention during dry periods. Most farmers also observed an increase in farm biodiversity, particularly in soil fauna and pollinators. A reduced incidence of pests was another commonly reported benefit.

These changes were mostly identified through visual observation, and in some cases, confirmed by periodic soil analyses. Conversations with colleagues using conventional management revealed that the AE farmers believe that agroecological soil management offers advantages, particularly in terms of crop resilience to critical challenges like water scarcity and co-benefits for the environment, such as increased biodiversity, maintenance or enhancement of soil organic matter, and reduced fuel consumption. However, they identified challenges in the transitioning to this type of management, which requires specific technical skills and flexibility.

The farmers' ratings of the parameters included in the ARTEMIS monitoring framework are presented in Table 8. They suggested incorporating the QBS-ar index and the use of moisture sensors into the monitoring program. They did not recommend excluding any of the indicators mentioned.

The farmers interviewed, many of whom are already participating in Living Lab initiatives that facilitate information sharing and soil monitoring campaigns, are open to allowing scientists to take specific measurements, collect soil samples from their fields, and provide information about their management practices. Other farmers in Spain have also expressed a willingness to collaborate with scientists; however, some prefer not to be part of an established network.

For data collection, the preferred methods for sharing management information are in-person interviews and phone calls. Additionally, the farmers mentioned that they would appreciate receiving the results of field measurements, along with a summary report detailing changes in the monitored parameters over time.

Table 8: Usefulness of the indicators and ecosystems services groups from the land users in the ARTEMIS network

	Indicator	Usefulness for monitoring (sensitiveness to agroecological management) in a scale 1 (not useful) to 5 (very useful)
Physical	Bulk density	5
	Penetration resistance	4-5
	Visual soil assessment for soil structure (VESS)	3-4
	Plant available water	5
Chemical	Total SOC content	5
	Total N	3-4
	Plant available P	3-4
	K	3-4
	pH	2 (up to 5 in farms with acid soils)
	Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	4-5
Biological	Earthworms	5
	Microbial activity	4-5
	Microbial Biomass	4-5
	Soil Cover	4-5
	Biomass production	4
	Crop yield	4-5
	Crop diversity	5
Inherent	Soil texture (Soil type)	3
	Climate and weather	5
Ecosystem services groups	Erosion control	2-4
	Flood regulation	4
	Greenhouse gas regulation and soil quality - Carbon sequestration	5
	Water quality	4-5

	Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	4-5
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Summary

It is not always easy to quantify or assign a value to the ecosystems provided by the soil (Boerema et al., 2017; Small et al., 2017). Even if the CICES is a good basis for addressing ESS in the context of soils and agricultural management, it is difficult to connect with direct or indirect indicators and also has certain limitations. These include overlaps, gaps, and class definitions that are either too specific or overly broad Paul et al., (2021). For example, while erosion control is explicitly included, other soil threats like compaction can only indirectly linked to ESS like water flow regulation. Additionally, services related to soil's role in filtering and remediating organic waste, and protect the soil water quality, could be grouped into broader categories rather than being overly specific. The same applies for services related to the biotic cultural services which in the context of agriculture and soils are too details and could be grouped. On the other hand, services like erosion control or improving soil quality through decomposition and fixing processes could be broken down into more specific categories, such as wind erosion control and water erosion control.

For the ARTEMIS monitoring framework, the project partners have selected the most important ESS (Table 5) related to climate change mitigation and adaptation and significant for the agricultural sustainability of European AE systems. We tried to identify direct and indirect indicators for the monitoring and evaluation of the impact of AE practices on these ESS at farm level. Direct and direct indicators were also identified for determining and monitoring soil health indicators (selected by project partners) (Table 6) in the different agroecological systems i.e. determining the chemical, physical and biological condition of the soil.

In Table 9, we aim to connect the various direct and indirect indicators proposed in the ARTEMIS monitoring framework with the relevant soil and agricultural management-related ESS identified as significant within the scope of ARTEMIS. Additionally, in Table 10 we seek to link the proposed soil health indicators with the three aspects of soil health as defined by the Soil Monitoring Law (EC, 2023), providing a comprehensive overview of how the monitoring framework aligns with both soil health and ESS monitoring objectives.

The establishment of a comprehensive on-farm monitoring system for soil health and ESS at the regional or national level is important. Such a system would provide valuable insights to a wide range of stakeholders, from policymakers and scientists to farmers, to improve the soil management practices and sustainability of the agricultural systems. For achieving these several needs were identified i.e.,

- a network of farmers willing to share detailed data and space for monitoring;
- a set of indicators that can be frequently monitor across the network;
- ensuring high-quality farm management and soil data;
- developing efficient methods and open-source farm management information systems (FMIS) for collecting and integrating data from multiple sources to support modelling and estimation of the indirect indicators;
- securing permanent funding for long-term monitoring and viability of the network;

Many of these goals can be achieved through the Living Lab (LL) approach, fostering collaboration sectors.

Table 9: Link of selected ecosystem services with the direct and indirect indicators proposed in the ARTEMIS monitoring framework

CICES V5.1 Group	Soil related ecosystems services that considered in the monitoring framework (CICES V5.1 class)	Related Indicators in the ARTEMIS framework	
		Indirect (models, tools, etc.)	Direct (measurable)
Biomass production	1.1.1.1: Cultivated terrestrial plants grown for nutritional purposes	Soil cover and biomass through RS; Plant available water through PTF	Total above ground biomass; N; P; K
Greenhouse gas regulation and soil quality	2.2.4.2: Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality; 2.2.6.1: Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere	Biogeochemical models; Ecosystem models;	BD; Total SOC;
Erosion and flood control	2.2.1.1: Control of erosion rates; 2.2.1.3: Hydrological cycle & water flow regulation (Including flood control)	-Soil cover through RS; -Soil water erosion rates/risk through: a. Soil tillage intensity rating (STIR index), b. Modelling and RS; -Soil compaction risk through Terranimo® model; -Hydrological modelling & RS	BD; Penetration resistance; VESS; SOC content of topsoil
Water quality	2.1.1.1, 2.1.1.2: Bioremediation / Filtration / sequestration / storage / accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals; 2.2.5.1: Chemical quality regulation of freshwaters	Indicator of Frequency of Treatment (IFT) for phytosanitary soil pollution risk	Total N; Plant available P; K; CEC
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	2.2.3.1, 2.2.3.2: Disease and pest control; 2.2.2.1, 2.2.2.3: Pollination, Maintaining nursery populations and habitats	Crop diversity: Shannon diversity index; Plant available water through PTF	VESS; Earthworms; Microbial activity; Microbial biomass

Table 10: Link of the direct and indirect indicators proposed in the ARTEMIS monitoring framework with the aspects of soil health (EC, 2023).

		Direct	Indirect	
Soil health <i>defined as " the physical, chemical, and biological condition of the soil determining its capacity to function as a vital living system and to provide ecosystem services (EC, 2023)</i>	Physical	Bulk density		
		Penetration resistance		
		Visual soil assessment for soil structure (VESS)		
		Plant available water		Estimation with pedotransfer function using measured data
	Chemical	Total SOC content		
		SOC stocks		Modelling & remote sensing
		Total N		
		Plant available P		
		K		
		pH		
		Cation exchange capacity (CEC)		
		C/N ratio		
	Biological	Earthworms		
		Microbial activity		
		Microbial Biomass		
		Soil Cover		Remote sensing
		Biomass production		Remote sensing
		Crop yield		Farmers information
		Crop diversity		Shannon diversity index
	Inherent	Soil type		Estimation from measured data
		Soil texture		Soil texture maps
Climatic conditions			Open access databases	

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Appendix

Table A1: The soil and management related ESS as scored by the survey participants presented from the most relevant to the least relevant. In the column "Rank" the average value of the ranking process is presented. With 1 to represent the most relevant and 3 the least relevant. With green colour the 25% of the highest-ranking ecosystem services, with yellow the 25-50 % ranked ESS and with orange the 50-100 %.

CICES V5.1 Group	CICES V5.1 class	Simple description in the CICES V5.1	CICES V5.1 code	Rank
Biomass production	Cultivated terrestrial plants (including fungi, algae) grown for nutritional purposes	Any crops and fruits grown by humans for food and feed	1.1.1.1	1.00
Erosion and flood control	Control of erosion rates	Controlling or preventing soil loss	2.2.1.1	1.00
GHG regulation and soil quality	Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality	Ensuring the organic matter is maintained	2.2.4.2	1.00
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	Disease control	Controlling disease	2.2.3.2	1.00
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	Pest control (including invasive species)	Controlling pests and invasive species	2.2.3.1	1.00
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	Pollination (or 'gamete' dispersal in a marine context)	Pollinating our fruit trees and other plants	2.2.2.1	1.14
Water quality	Bioremediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	Decomposing wastes	2.1.1.1	1.29
Water quality	Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	Filtering wastes	2.1.1.2	1.29
Water quality	Regulation of the chemical condition of freshwaters by living processes	Controlling the chemical quality of freshwater	2.2.5.1	1.29
Erosion and flood control	Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (including flood control, and coastal protection)	Regulating the flows of water in our environment	2.2.1.3	1.29
GHG regulation and soil quality	Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans	Regulating our global climate	2.2.6.1	1.29
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	Maintaining nursery populations and habitats (including gene pool protection)	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us	2.2.2.3	1.29
Water supply	Ground (and subsurface) water for drinking	Dirking water from the below ground	4.2.2.1	1.43
Erosion and flood control	Buffering and attenuation of mass movement	Stopping landslides and avalanches harming people	2.2.1.2	1.43
Erosion and flood control	Liquid flows	Physical barriers to flows	5.2.1.2	1.50
Water supply	Surface water for drinking	Drinking water from sources at the ground surface	4.2.1.1	1.57
Recreation, culture, and education	Characteristics of living systems that that enable activities promoting health, recuperation, or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions	Using the environment for sport and recreation; using	3.1.1.1	1.57

		nature to help stay fit		
Protection from further nuisances, extreme events, and weather conditions	Regulation of temperature and humidity, including ventilation and transpiration	Regulating the physical quality of air for people	2.2.6.2	1.71
Recreation, culture, and education	Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation, or enjoyment through passive or observational interactions	Watching plants and animals where they live; using nature to destress	3.1.1.2	1.71
Biomass production	Fibres and other materials from cultivated plants, fungi, algae and bacteria for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)	Material from plants, fungi, algae or bacterial that we can use as raw materials for non-nutritional purposes	1.1.1.2	1.86
Protection from further nuisances, extreme events, and weather conditions	Fire protection	Protecting people from fire	2.2.1.5	1.86
Recreation, culture, and education	Characteristics of living systems that enable education and training	Studying nature	3.1.2.2	1.86
Water quality	Mediation by other chemical or physical means (e.g., via filtration, sequestration, storage, or accumulation)	Natural processing of wastes	5.1.1.3	2.00
Water supply	Surface water used as a material (non-drinking purposes)	Surface water that we can use for things other than drinking	4.2.1.2	2.00
Water supply	Ground water (and subsurface) used as a material (non-drinking purposes)	Sub-surface water that we can use for things other than drinking	4.2.2.2	2.00
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	Seeds, spores, and other plant materials collected for maintaining or establishing a population	Seed collection	1.2.1.1	2.00
Recreation, culture, and education	Characteristics of living systems that enable aesthetic experiences	The beauty of nature	3.1.2.4	2.00
GHG regulation and soil quality	Weathering processes and their effect on soil quality	Ensuring soils form and develop	2.2.4.1	2.14
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	Seed dispersal	Spreading the seeds of wild plants	2.2.2.2	2.14
Pollination and biodiversity maintenance	Higher and lower plants (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties	Plants fungi or algae that we can use for breeding	1.2.1.2	2.14
Recreation, culture, and education	Characteristics of living systems that are resonant in terms of culture or heritage	The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	3.1.2.3	2.14
Recreation, culture, and education	Characteristics or features of living systems that have an option or bequest value	The things in nature that we want future generations to enjoy or use	3.2.2.2	2.14
Water quality	Regulation of the chemical condition of salt waters by living processes	Controlling the chemical quality of salt water	2.2.5.2	2.29

Supply minerals and raw materials	Mineral substances used for nutritional purposes	Minerals in our food	4.3.1.1	2.29
Protection from further nuisances, extreme events, and weather conditions	Wind protection	Protecting people from winds	2.2.1.4	2.29
Recreation, culture, and education	Characteristics of living systems that enable scientific investigation or the creation of traditional ecological knowledge	Researching nature	3.1.2.1	2.29
Biomass production	Cultivated plants (including fungi, algae) grown as a source of energy	Plant materials used as a source of energy	1.1.1.3	2.43
Protection from further nuisances, extreme events, and weather conditions	Visual screening	Screening unsightly things	2.1.2.3	2.43
Protection from further nuisances, extreme events, and weather conditions	Smell reduction	*Reducing smells	2.1.2.1	2.43
Protection from further nuisances, extreme events, and weather conditions	Noise attenuation	*Reducing noise	2.1.2.2	2.43
Recreation, culture, and education	Characteristics or features of living systems that have an existence value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	3.2.2.1	2.43
Biomass production	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used for nutrition	Food from wild plants	1.1.5.1	2.57
Supply minerals and raw materials	Mineral substances used for material purposes	Natural inorganic materials from nature we can use	4.3.1.2	2.57
Recreation, culture, and education	Elements of living systems that have symbolic meaning	Using nature to as a national or local emblem	3.2.1.1	2.57
Recreation, culture, and education	Elements of living systems that have sacred or religious meaning	The things in nature that have spiritual	3.2.1.2	2.57
Biomass production	Fibres and other materials from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)	Materials from wild plants	1.1.5.2	2.71
Biomass production	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used as a source of energy	Materials from wild plants, fungi and algae used for energy	1.1.5.3	2.71
Recreation, culture, and education	Elements of living systems used for entertainment or representation	The things in nature used to make films or to write books	3.2.1.3	2.71

*These ESS are not included in (Paul et al., 2021) classification

Table A2: The soil health indicators as scored by the survey participants presented from the most relevant to the least relevant. In the column "Rank" the average value of the ranking process is presented. With 1 to represent the most relevant and 3 the least relevant. With green colour the 25% of the highest-ranking indicators, with yellow the 25-50% ranked indicators and with orange the 50-100%.

Type	Indicator	Rank
Chemical	Total and potential mineralizable N	1.08
Chemical	Total soil organic carbon (SOC) content	1.15
Chemical	pH	1.15
Biological	Crop yield	1.15
Physical	Dry bulk density (ρ_b)	1.23
Biological	Soil cover	1.23
"Inherent"	Texture	1.23
"Inherent"	Precipitation	1.23
Chemical	SOC stock	1.25
Biological	Biomass production	1.25
"Inherent"	Climate	1.25
Chemical	Exchangeable K, Ca, Na, Mg	1.31
Chemical	Total soil organic matter (SOM)	1.33
Chemical	C/N ratio	1.38
"Inherent"	Soil type	1.38
Physical	Plant-available water	1.42
Chemical	Easily degradable organic matter (Hot water extractable C - HWC)	1.42
Biological	Earthworms	1.42
Physical	Moisture content	1.46
Physical	Water holding capacity/Field capacity	1.46
Physical	Signs of erosion	1.46
Chemical	Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	1.46
"Inherent"	Slope (gradient and length)	1.46
Chemical	Plant-available P (P-CaCl ₂)	1.50
Biological	Crop yield quality	1.50
Biological	Crop/plant diversity	1.50
"Inherent"	Risk of erosion	1.50
Physical	Penetration resistance	1.54
Chemical	Electrical conductivity (EC)	1.54
"Inherent"	Extreme weather events	1.54
Physical	Wilting point	1.58
Biological	Fungi/bacteria ratio	1.58
Physical	Visual soil assessment	1.62
Chemical	Total P (P-Al)	1.62
Physical	Surface sealing	1.67
Chemical	POXC (permanganate oxidizable carbon)	1.67
Biological	Microbial activity	1.67
Physical	Soil aggregate stability	1.69
Chemical	Micronutrients (B, Cu, Fe, Mn, Se, Si, Zn, etc.)	1.69
Biological	Microbial biomass	1.69
"Inherent"	Drainage class	1.69
"Inherent"	Rock fragments (>2mm)	1.69
Biological	Soil respiration	1.77
Biological	Rooting depth	1.77
Biological	Soil enzymes	1.83
Biological	Bacterial population	1.85
Biological	Fungal population	1.85
Physical	Infiltration rate	1.92
Physical	(Saturated) hydraulic conductivity	1.92
Physical	Water potential	1.92
Biological	Soil fauna	1.92
Chemical	Pesticide concentrations	1.92
Physical	Soil depth (horizons)	2.00
Physical	Standing water	2.00
Chemical	Heavy metals (Al, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn)	2.00

Chemical	Other organic pollutants, (e.g., polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, fluorinated chemicals 'PFAS', (micro)plastics, hormones, medicines)	2.00
Physical	Groundwater levels	2.08
Chemical	Corg/clay ratio	2.08
Biological	Pests and root diseases	2.08
Biological	Field wildlife (e.g., birds, mammals, insects)	2.08
Physical	Pore size distribution	2.15
Physical	Air capacity	2.15
Biological	Root density	2.15
Biological	Feeding activity	2.17
Chemical	Hot water extractable P (HWP)	2.25
Biological	Nematodes	2.25
Biological	Weed infestation	2.31
Physical	Packing density	2.33
Physical	Soil temperature	2.38
Chemical	S stock	2.38
Physical	Air permeability	2.50
Physical	Clay dispersibility	2.73
Physical	Air diffusivity	2.73